

THE ROLE OF MODERN INTERACTIVE METHODS IN TEACHING PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS ON EQUIPMENT

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Abstract: in this article, thoughts and opinions about the role of modern interactive methods in providing an understanding of this topic together with the methods of teaching common nouns to elementary school students are expressed. This article is relevant in that it reflects practical application guidelines along with providing theoretical information about modern interactive methods. The methods were developed on the basis of four stages in primary classes.

Key words: related noun, proper noun, spelling, dictionary, parallel, program, demand, person, thing, subject, meaning, speech, technology, development, method, thought, creative thinking.

Learning the vocabulary of nouns is a consistent and dependent process, and creating an understanding of this vocabulary for primary school students is a somewhat complicated and skillful process. A number of requirements and tasks are set before the student on the basis of the educational program in forming an understanding of each word group. In the process of studying nouns, the requirements for primary school students are as follows:

Forming a general grammatical understanding of nouns;

Distinguishing the spiritual groups of the noun from each other by questioning, that is, who? The words in the noun group that take the question are personal nouns; what? Interrogative nouns are object nouns; where? Forming skills and qualifications that the horses that receive the question are considered place horses;

To give an understanding of the spelling rules related to proper nouns (this term is not used by primary school students, they are simply called personal names), i.e. names of people, surnames, patronymics, names of animals and places. Spelling; Introduction to the concept of number in nouns (singular and plural nouns);

Formation of skills and competences about the categories of possession and agreement in nouns, their types in the case they are received, and the rules related to spelling:

To prepare the ground for enriching the vocabulary with words from the noun group, to be able to use them in speech without any mistakes;

They should know how to analyze, compare and generalize words [1].

This word group is distinguished by its lexical meanings and grammatical signs. But all nouns have a common lexical meaning, which is considered to represent a person and a thing. That's what scientific observation and experiments are all about shows that elementary school students are taught nouns not in an in-depth state, but through simple, simple information. Although the formation of basic knowledge about this word group in the minds of students begins in the second half of the first grade, this process expands a little from the second half of the second grade. That is, at this stage, giving knowledge about lexical meaning, proper nouns and similar nouns deepens a bit. To form an understanding of the word family, it is important to divide the nouns included in this word family into the main lexical groups, to show the signs characteristic of all nouns and their place in our speech. For this purpose, words denoting person and thing are put into one system from the first stages of understanding about nouns. Based on this, nouns denoting people, plants and creatures, objects, natural phenomena and events are divided into groups [2].

In this process, students begin to distinguish words that are part of the noun group. In this, the skill of comparing and distinguishing is formed in their minds. The skill of distinguishing common and related nouns is also formed in this process,

which belongs to the second class. By showing the comparison to the students, the different sides of nouns of the same kind and nouns (without nouns) are highlighted. When giving an understanding of related nouns, the term “related noun” is not used, they are named according to the groups in their composition, that is, nouns that mean a person – personal nouns; nouns denoting the meaning of things – nouns of things; Nouns expressing the meaning of place are called place-nouns. Famous nouns are named after expressing a name. The main difference between them is in their spelling, proper nouns (names of persons, things and places) are written with a capital letter regardless of where they appear in the sentence. Methods are the tools that most closely serve to easily convey this process, which is a bit complicated for young children, to students.

The role of modern interactive methods in education

Modern interactive methods are considered to be a useful tool for obtaining high results without spending a lot of effort. At the same time, it helps the children who have just moved away from playing activities to gain interest and attention in the lesson. These methods deliver the same topic to the student through different methods. It develops creative thinking and innovative ideas, which play a key role in rapidly developing education based on foreign experiences. But not all interactive methods are successful and give effective and positive results. There are several requirements and conditions for this, which are as follows:

The chosen method should be suitable for the student’s age, psychology and physiological capabilities;

Selection based on class capabilities;

Conform to the essence of the topic;

And most importantly, it should be properly organized.

Through this scientific article, we have tried to highlight a number of interactive methods through examples in order to create an understanding of common nouns among primary school students, and we think that these methods

will have a positive effect. In the process of explaining this topic, the teacher can closely use modern interactive methods such as “Fan”, “Pen on the table”, “Energizers”, “Pillapoya”, “Bermurd triangle”. We will explain how to organize the above methods through examples. On behalf of the majority, it is decided that the interactive method “Bermurd’s triangle” is suitable only for mathematics. But this decision cannot be considered correct, because this method is considered a multi-functional interactive method in terms of its application. This method imposes several requirements on the teacher:

In this case, the capabilities of the class should be at a slightly higher level, that is, larger. Because the teacher should draw a triangle shape on the floor.

Since the students are divided into three groups, they should be divided into three groups according to the answers to the questions.

The Bermuda Triangle interactive method is organized in the following form:

In this case, the teacher must have a pre-made plan and preparation;

A triangle should be drawn on the floor, i.e. in front of the blackboard;

The questions should be made using information from three parts, i.e. related nouns (person, object, place nouns).

For example, in a simple form, one side of a triangle is written with a person, the other with an object, and the third with place nouns. When the teacher reads a noun from the list to the student, the student recognizes it and goes to that side of the triangle. Will have to live.

The number of students depends on the discretion of the teacher and must be at least three.

Through this method, not only the thoughts and opinions within the subject, but also the skills of mobility, resourcefulness and quickness of young students increase. They come to a decision in a very short period of time and learn to move (this process is reflected in the fact that the student, after hearing the noun phrase

read by the teacher, makes a decision and takes a place on one side of the triangle).

The ability to focus attention is formed.

The method explained above through examples can help not only in the framework of strengthening a new or past topic, but also in forming an initial understanding of a new topic. In addition, this method closely supports the integration of mathematics and mother tongue. One of the methods recommended above for forming the initial concepts about the related noun “Energizers” is formed in the following order:

The advantage of this method is that it is superior to the teacher does not require a level of opportunity and preparation;

It increases happiness and encourages students to wake up. But it is recommended only for students of the fourth grade, not for the 1st, 2nd, and 3rd grades. Because this method requires the student to have mastered the syllable and the skills related to it.

Students sitting at desks are divided into three groups by choosing a three-syllable word and dividing it into three parts.

First, a student is chosen from among those sitting and placed behind the door, because he should not hear the word.

After that, the students say the related noun divided into syllables together, and the student on the board will have to find which word it is.

This method is organized within the repetition of the subject. Through this method, it is shown how attentive the students were in the process of explaining the topic and how well they retained the words related to the same noun in their memory.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be said that the role of modern interactive methods in creating an understanding of any subject in elementary school students and achieving a positive result is incomparable. It is a tool that closely serves the

student's self-confidence, including the formation of creative ideas, ingenuity, and responsiveness.

List of used literature:

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